

Another twisted malacological riddle: *Chauvetia elongata* Nordsieck & García-Talavera, 1979 (Gastropoda, Buccinoidea, Chauvetiidae)

Otro enigma malacológico retorcido: *Chauvetia elongata* Nordsieck & García-Talavera, 1979 (Gastropoda, Buccinoidea, Chauvetiidae)

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ABSTRACT

The original description of the taxon *Chauvetia elongata* Nordsieck & García-Talavera, 1979 lacks many distinguishing features, with few not accurate or vague data. Herein, the true identity of this taxon is established with a re-description of the species, and with the designation of a neotype to stabilize the nomenclature. The type material of *Pleurotoma pellisphocae* Reeve, 1845 and *Lachesis retifera* Brugnone, 1880, is figured. These two names were wrongly used to denote *C. elongata*, as misidentifications by several European authors. For all these taxa, a critical historical review is provided.

RESUMEN

La descripción original del taxón *Chauvetia elongata* Nordsieck & García-Talavera, 1979 carece de muchas características distintivas, con pocos datos no precisos o vagos. Aquí se establece la correcta identidad de este taxón con una redescrición de la especie y con la designación de un neotipo para estabilizar la nomenclatura. Se figura el material tipo de *Pleurotoma pellisphocae* Reeve, 1845 y *Lachesis retifera* Brugnone, 1880. Estos dos nombres se utilizaron indebidamente para designar a *C. elongata*, como identificaciones erróneas por parte de varios autores europeos. Para todos estos taxones, se proporciona una revisión histórica crítica.

KEY WORDS: Gastropoda, Buccinidae, *Chauvetia*, Pseudomelatomidae, *Crassispira*, systematics, neotype designation, Mediterranean Sea, northwestern Africa.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Gastropoda, Buccinidae, *Chauvetia*, Pseudomelatomidae, *Crassispira*, sistemática, designación de neotipo, mar Mediterráneo, noroeste de África.

INTRODUCTION

After thousands of malacological papers and extensive research, the true identity or the correct name to be used

for several taxa are still an unsolved question. This is due to errors or misidentifications in recent and past

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bibliography. Other occasional events (i.e. loss or mess of type material) are or have been cause of hustle and bustle in taxonomic and nomenclatural issues.

This context can be applied to some species of the genus *Chauvetia* Monterosato, 1884, where the delimitation of the species is based widely on the shell features only. *Chauvetia* is a enigmatic genus of buccinid gastropods, with a distributional range in the eastern Atlantic from the English Channel to Senegal, and the Mediterranean Sea (OLIVER & ROLÁN, 2008, 2009; GOFAS & OLIVER, 2010; LANDAU, DA SILVA & VERMEIJ, 2015; LANDAU & MICALI, 2023). Most of the species are intertidal to subtidal, only a few occurring in deep water (HOFFMAN, FRAUSSEN & FREIWALD, 2018). Recently, the genus was reassessed (in part) using molecular data and radula features (KANTOR ET AL., 2022 [2021]), with the establishment of the new family Chauvetiidae Kantor, Fedosov, Kosyan, Puillandre, Sorokin, Kano, Clark & Bouchet, 2021, for the *Chauvetia*-clade, as a sister group to the Pisaniidae Gray, 1857.

Chauvetia has a very confusing systematics history, well explained by HOFFMAN ET AL. (2018). This genus was published simultaneously with *Folineaea* Monterosato, 1884, and the precedence of the names must be fixed by the first reviser (ICZN art. 24.2.2). COSSMANN (1896) treated *Chauvetia* and *Folineaea* as junior synonyms of *Donovania* Bucquoy, Dautzenberg & Dollfus, 1883. PALLARY

(1902), ignoring the work of COSSMANN (1896), proposed *Adansonia* as new name pro *Folineaea*, because the root of the name was the same as for *Folinia* Crosse, 1868, but the names are not homonyms (ICZN art. 56.2), and the nomenclatural act of Pallary was unnecessary. IREDALE (1918), proposed *Syntagma* as new name pro *Donovania*. THIELE (1929) seems to be the first to adopt the use of *Chauvetia* as a valid name, with *Folineaea* quoted as junior synonym, and rejecting *Donovania*.

At present WoRMS lists 42 extant species of *Chauvetia*, and a few questionable taxa (WoRMS, 2024). Among these, the true identity of *Chauvetia* (*Folinia*) *elongata* Nordsieck & García-Talavera, 1979, is a very intricate question, mostly due to the misidentification with other two taxa: *Lachesis retifera* Brugnone, 1880 and *Pleurotoma pellisphocae* Reeve, 1845, given by several European authors.

Abbreviations:

- MNHN: Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France.
- NHMUK: Natural History Museum London, United Kingdom.
- NMNH: National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution, Washington DC, USA.
- RMNH: Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, The Netherlands.
- CNI: Nofroni Italo collection - Rome, Italy.
- CRW: Renda Walter collection - Amantea, Italy.

SYSTEMATICS

GASTROPODA Couvier, 1795

NEOGASTROPODA Wenz, 1938

CONOIDEA Fleming, 1822

PSEUDOMELATOMIDAE Morrison, 1966

Crassispira Swainson, 1840

Crassispira pellisphocae (Reeve, 1845) (Figs. 1A-C; 6A)

Pleurotoma pellisphocae Reeve, 1845 - original combination.

Pleurotoma cancellata Reeve, 1846 - junior subjective synonym.

Clathrodrillia limans Dall, 1919 - junior subjective synonym.

Type material: *Pleurotoma pellisphocae*, one syntype in NHMUK 1879.2.26.43. *Pleurotoma cancellata*, two syntypes in NHMUK, 1875.4.26.17 - St. Vincent, West Indies. *Clathrodrillia limans*, holotype in NMNH, 56218.

Type locality: not stated in original description. Subsequently designated as Union Island, St. Vincent and Grenadines (FALLON, 2011).

Original description: “*Pleurotoma testâ pyramidali, anfractibus convexis, longitudinaliter fortiter et creberrimè granulatis, transversim subsulcatis aperturâ peculiariter parvâ, sinu indistincto.*”

Remarks: *Crassispira pellisphocae* is a species of Pseudomelatomidae, from the Caribbean Sea (MAES, 1983; FABER, 2007; FALLON, 2011), although many European authors mistakenly applied Reeve’s specific name to denote *Chauvetia elongata* Nordsieck & García-Talavera, 1979.

REEVE (1845) did not indicate the type locality, and gave an inadequate description with a misleading figure, which at first glance could resemble a species of *Chauvetia*. However, the true identification of this taxon as a species belonging the genus *Crassispira* Swainson, 1840, is based on the type material in NHMUK, a specimen recognized as the holotype by MAES (1983) and FALLON (2011). This specimen is illustrated in FABER (2007: fig. 27) and FALLON (2011: fig. 24). Anyway, in the original description, Reeve did not report if the new species was based on a single specimen, and therefore, the type material must be recognized as a syntype (ICZN art. 73.2.1).

The same Reeve, in 1846, described *Pleurotoma cancellata* from St. Vincent, West Indies. TOMLIN (1934) considered this taxon as junior synonym of *Pleurotoma pellisphocae*, and this was confirmed by MAES (1983) and FALLON (2011) after examination of the two syntypes in NHMUK 1875.4.26.17.

TRYON (1884) placed this species in the genus *Lachesis* Risso, 1826, an invalid synonym of *Chauvetia* Monterosato, 1884, but within the family Pleurotomidae Gray, 1838. The author gave a figure that resemble the species of Reeve. This supraspecific assignment is ambiguous, because of the confuse idea of *Lachesis* sensu Tryon, as a genus of Pleurotomi-

dae, and not of Buccinidae, and in which the author lists species belonging different families.

DAUTZENBERG (1917) reported a species under this specific name, from the Atlantic coast of Morocco, but without illustrations, and in the genus *Donovania*, B.D D., 1883, another invalid synonym of *Chauvetia* Monterosato, 1884. Obviously, Dautzenberg did not refer to Reeve’s species from Caribbean Sea, but to a different species of *Chauvetia* from the eastern Atlantic, and therefore this record must be treated as a misidentification.

DALL (1919) described *Clathrodrillia limans*, erroneously from Gulf of California (McLean in KEEN, 1971; MAES, 1983), on the basis of a single specimens: “*This shell was sent to Dr. Philip Carpenter by Stearns and returned to him with the above manuscript name, but never published.*”. This shell is the holotype by monotypy (ICZN art. 73.2.1). The taxon was considered as junior synonym of *Pleurotoma pellisphocae* by TOMLIN (1934), and this was confirmed by MAES (1983) and recently by FALLON (2011).

PALLARY (1920) figured a specimen of *Chauvetia elongata* Nordsieck & García-Talavera, 1979, under the name *Donovania (Adansonia) pellisphocae* Reeve, 1843. The author meant the *Lachesis retifera* Brugnone, 1880 sensu MONTEROSATO (1884, 1889), and this double misidentification caused trouble to many subsequent authors. In fact, after this, usage of the specific name *pellisphocae* (REEVE, 1843) or *retifera* (BRUGNONE, 1880) sensu *auctores* has become accustomed (see discussion on *C. retifera*). Pallary proposed also two varieties “*ex. colore*”: *zonata* and *lactea*, without any description, illustration or reference, therefore in addition to their infrasubspecific rank, these name are nomina nuda. TOMLIN (1934) also wrongly proposed that *P. pellisphocae* belongs to the genus *Chauvetia*.

MAES (1983) placed *Pleurotoma pellisphocae* in the genus *Crassispira* (*Monilispira*) Bartsch & Rehder, 1939, as a turrid gastropod. The systematics of *Crassispira* and *Monilispira* was revisited by BOUCHET ET AL. (2011), and at present day both are recognized as valid genera within the family Pseudomelatomidae. FABER (2007) reported the species in the genus *Monilispira*, and pointed out the mistake made by several European authors, in the use of *P. pellisphocae* for an eastern Atlantic member of the buccinid genus *Chauvetia*.

Recently, LANDAU & MICALI (2023), without explication, wrongly listed *C. pel-*

lisphocae as a living species from Mediterranean Sea and northwestern Africa.

To summarize, *Pleurotoma pellisphocae* was wrongly confused with *Chauvetia elongata* and *C. retifera*, by many authors, in some cases as a single species with *P. pellisphocae* as oldest available name, in other cases with *C. retifera* as a separate species, and *C. elongata* a junior synonym of *P. pellisphocae*. Anyway, the type material in NHMUK, reveals that the species of Reeve, is not a buccinoid gastropod, but a species in the genus *Crassispira*, belonging to the family Pseudomelatomidae.

BUCCINOIDEA Rafinesque, 1815

CHAUVETIIDAE Kantor, Fedosov, Kosyan, Puillandre, Sorokin, Kano, R. Clark & Bouchet, 2021

Chauvetia Monterosato, 1884

- = *Lachesis* Risso, 1826 - invalid, junior homonym of *Lachesis* Daudin, 1803 [Reptilia];
- = *Nesaea* Risso, 1826 - invalid, junior homonym of *Nesaea* Leach, 1814 [Crustacea];
- = *Donovania* B. D. D., 1883 - invalid, junior homonym of *Donovania* Leach, 1814 [Crustacea];
- = *Folineaea* Monterosato, 1884 - junior subjective synonym;
- = *Donovania* (*Adansonia*) Pallary, 1902 - unnecessary nomen novum pro *Folineaea* Monterosato, 1884;
- = *Syntagma* Iredale, 1918 - unnecessary nomen novum pro *Donovania* B. D. D., 1883
- = *Donovaniella* Nordsieck, 1968 - junior subjective synonym;
- = *Folinia* [sic] Monterosato, 1889 - not available, misspelling of *Folineaea* Monterosato, 1884; not *Folinia* Crosse, 1868.

† *Chauvetia retifera* (Brugnone, 1880) (Fig. 2A-F)

Lachesis retifera Brugnone, 1880 - original combination.

Type material: holotype in Museo di Paleontologia del Dipartimento di Scienze Biologiche, Geologiche e Ambientali dell'Università di Catania (Italy), 1198/13-33.

Type locality: Giannettello (now Contrada Giannettello), near Caltanissetta, Sicily, Italy. Upper Pliocene - Lower Pleistocene (REITANO ET AL., 2019)

Original description: "Conchiglia minuta, ovato-turrita, con apice ottuso e levigato, lunga mm. 6¼, larga mm. 2½: anfratti 7, leggermente convessi, separati da suture poco profonde, sottilmente reticolati: reticolo formato da linee poco elevate o costicine longitudinali e spirali, le une e le altre uguali tra loro ed ai loro intervalli, perlate nel loro incrociamiento e formanti tante piccole areole incavate e quadrate come le maglie d'una rete; linee longitudinali rette,

esistenti dalla seconda metà del primo giro, 24 nell'ultimo, quasi mancanti nella coda; linee spirali o trasverse protratte dal secondo giro sino a tutta la coda, 13 nell'ultimo giro, 5 nel penultimo, 3 negli altri: apertura rotondata, coda cortissima, columella contorta; labbro destro acuto, internamente munito di 5 pieghe grosse, che cominciano sopra il canaletto ma non arrivano in alto; labbro sinistro tenue, distinto e continuo col destro."

Figure 1. *Crassispira pellisphocae* (Reeve, 1845), A-C: syntype (9.2 mm) without locality data, NHMUK 1879.2.26.43.

Figura 1. *Crassispira pellisphocae* (Reeve, 1845), A-C: sintipo (9,2 mm) sin datos de localidad, NHMUK 1879.2.26.43.

Remarks: BRUGNONE (1880) described *L. retifera* as a fossil species from the Upper Pliocene-Lower Pleistocene of Sicily, on the basis of a single specimen, as pointed out in the text: “Fondo questa specie sopra un esemplare d’una rara scultura e conservatissimo”. This specimen must be recognized as holotype fixed by monotypy (ICZN art. 73.2.1), despite it was quoted as probably lectotype in REITANO *ET AL.* (2019).

The original type material was considered lost (TRINGALI, 2001), until 2008, when Mrs. Laura Ryolo, heir of Monterosato, donated 140 lots of the collection of Monterosato to the Dipartimento di Scienze Geologiche dell’Università di Catania, now Museo di Paleontologia del Dipartimento di Scienze Biologiche, Geologiche e Ambientali dell’Università di Catania, Italy. In these lots, the type material of *Lachesis retifera* was discovered.

This is due to the acquisition by Monterosato of the collection of Brugnone (MONTEROSATO, 1915; TRINGALI, 2001; APPOLLONI *ET AL.*, 2018; REITANO *ET AL.*, 2019), probably in 1884 (GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI, 1982: p. X; 1983: 655).

This rediscovery revealed the true identity of this species, solving the questions about the misidentification with *C. elongata* and/or *C. pellisphocae* sensu Pallary, 1920, by several recent and past authors, due to an inaccurate original iconography, and to the report in Monterosato of Brugnone’s species from the Atlantic coast of Morocco (see discussion under *C. elongata*).

Brugnone’s species differs from *C. elongata* in having a less slender profile, higher number of spiral cords, more tiny and reticulate sculpture, and a smaller protoconch, with less numerous but more elevated axial ribs. According to

REITANO ET AL. (2019), *C. retifera* must be regarded as a fossil species from the Upper Pliocene - Lower Pleistocene of Sicily, Italy, while *C. elongata* is a different

Recent species from northwestern Africa, western Iberian Peninsula and westernmost Mediterranean Sea (MICALI, 1999; TRINGALI, 2001; GOFAS & OLIVER, 2010).

Chauvetia elongata Nordsieck & García-Talavera, 1979 (Figs. 3-5; 6B, C)

Chauvetia (Folinia) elongata Nordsieck & García-Talavera, 1979 - original combination.

Type material: neotype here designated, MNHN, IM-2000-39065.

Neotype locality: Sables d'Or beach, Temara, Morocco. 33°55' N, 07°00' W. Rocks and silt, 0-2 m.

Description: small pupoid and thick shell, up to 12 mm (neotype 9.5 mm), elongate, not scalariform. Protoconch of ca. 1.25 whorls, whitish, with 13-15 moderately elevated ribs and a tenuous microsculpture, only visible under the SEM, of irregular, very fine, anastomosing spiral threads. Transition to teleoconch not well defined, starts with teleoconch sculpture. Teleoconch of 6.5 narrow whorls, with a weakly canalculated suture. Spiral sculpture of 10-11 low and moderately broad cords, smooth or with low tubercles. Axial sculpture of last whorl with 20-30 rounded and low ribs. Aperture whitish, rounded-ovate, with a weak labral varix. Outer lip smooth or with 4-6 internal denticles. Columellar lip smooth. Siphonal canal very short. Color creamish, orangish, brownish, pale to very dark, sometimes with one or two darker spiral bands.

Remarks: *Chauvetia (Folinia) elongata* was established by NORDSIECK & GARCÍA-TALAVERA (1979) from Gran Canaria. The authors gave a description, a drawing, and reported that the holotype is preserved in the Museo de Ciencias Naturales de Santa Cruz de Tenerife (now incorporated in Museo de la Naturaleza y el Hombre de Tenerife), while several paratypes are preserved in the private collection of Bernard Zoder.

A great confusion surrounds this taxon since the 19th century. It is only rather recently that the species was described, but it was known from northwestern Africa by past authors since long time, always misidentified with either *Lachesis retifera* Brugnone, 1880 or *Pleurotoma pellisphocae* Reeve, 1845. Fur-

thermore, the presence of the species in the type locality is doubtful, not confirmed by OLIVER & ROLÁN (2009) nor by HERNÁNDEZ ET AL. (2011).

Confusion begins with MONTEROSATO (1884), who listed in his new genus *Folineaea*, the *Lachesis retifera* of Brugnone, as living and coming from "Gibraltar, Tanger, Asturias and Mogador". *Folineaea* is currently treated as a junior synonym of *Chauvetia* (WORMS, 2024). For some subsequent authors, Monterosato meant the species later described as *C. elongata*, but this is only tentative and very questionable, because without a description and illustrations, there is no certainty of what is *Lachesis retifera sensu* Monterosato. This uncertainty is increased by the presence in west Africa of a few closely species such as *C. lefebvrii* (Maravigna, 1840), *C. tenuisculpta* (Dautzenberg, 1891), *C. luciacuestae* Oliver & Rolán, 2008 and *C. austeri* Oliver & Rolán, 2009. Furthermore, the author proposed the synonymy with *Lachesis dolioliformis*, which is his own undescribed species. This latter name was first published as synonym, and therefore it is not available (ICZN art. 11.6, 12.2.1 and 12.3).

Before 1889, Monterosato probably held Brugnone's collection, and therefore the holotype of *L. retifera*, but the author again placed Brugnone's species in the genus *Folinia* ([sic!] misspelling for *Folineaea*) and coming from "Tanger, Casa Blanca, Mogador, Vigo, Gibraltar and Asturias", reporting again the synonymy with his undescribed species *L. dolioliformis* ([sic!] misspelling for *dolioliformis*). The type of Brugnone's species has a different shape compared to *C. elongata*, and

Figure 2. *Chauvetia retifera* (Brugnone, 1880). A-D: holotype of *Lachesis retifera* (6.3 mm), Museo di Paleontologia del Dipartimento di Scienze Biologiche, Geologiche e Ambientali dell'Università di Catania, Italy, 1198/13-33; E: original drawing; F: original handwritten label.

Figura 2. *Chauvetia retifera* (Brugnone, 1880). A-D: holotipo de *Lachesis retifera* (6,3 mm), Museo di Paleontologia del Dipartimento di Scienze Biologiche, Geologiche e Ambientali dell'Università di Catania, Italia, 1198/13-33; E: dibujo original; F: eticheta manuscrita original.

Figure 3. *Chauvetia elongata* Nordsieck & García-Talavera, 1979. A-G: Temara, Morocco (9.5 mm), neotype here designated, MNHN-IM-2000-39065.

Figura 3. *Chauvetia elongata* Nordsieck & García-Talavera, 1979. A-G: Temara, Marruecos (9.5 mm), neotipo aquí designado, MNHN-IM-2000-39065.

Figure 4. *Chauvetia elongata* Nordsieck & García-Talavera, 1979. A: juvenile specimen, Temara, Morocco, same sample as the neotype, MNHN IM-2010-6653; B: apical view of another specimen; C: microsculpture of protoconch.

Figura 4. *Chauvetia elongata* Nordsieck & García-Talavera, 1979. A: ejemplar juvenil, Temara, Marruecos, misma muestra que el neotipo, MNHN IM-2010-6653; B: vista apical; C: microescultura de la protoconcha.

therefore, *retifera sensu* Monterosato is a different species from the Atlantic coast of Morocco. MONTEROSATO (1889) also proposed three new varieties from “Casa Blanca”: var. *lirifera*: “Dans cette forme prédominent les éléments spiraux.”; var. *glomulus*: “Petite forme très ventrue et acuminée à la pointe; réticulation comme dans le type.” and var. *labrosa*: “Très trapue et épaisse, surtout à l’ouverture.”. All these names lack illustrations and were introduced with a very minimal description, which is not useful for their correct identification. The type material or other lots of *Chauvetia* sp. of Monterosato were not found in Museo Civico di Zoologia di Roma (MCZR) (Appolloni comm. pers.), and are presumably lost. The three varieties of Monterosato, without original type material, illustrations and with a useless description, must be considered as *nomina dubia*, because there is no certainty of what Monterosato meant. Even a rediscovery of Monterosato’s types doesn’t change anything, because these

names are considered to be of an infrasubspecific rank, and therefore not available (IZCN: art. 1.3.4 and 45.5): all from the same locality; proposed as “var.”; and about *lirifera* and *labrosa*, Monterosato wrote expressly “forme”. This denotes that the author gave them an infrasubspecific rank.

Chauvetia elongata was misidentified with *C. retifera* by many authors. Probably this is due to PALLARY (1902, 1920), who wrongly applied the specific name *Donovania* (*Adansonia*) *pellisphocae*, while Reeve’s species does not belong to the Buccinoidea (FALLON, 2011; WORMS, 2024), see discussion under *Crassispira pellisphocae* (Reeve 1845). PALLARY (1902) listed *Donovania* (*Adansonia*) *pellisphocae* Reeve, 1845 from “la Baie de Tanger”, Morocco, and also indicated as doubtful synonym *Lachesis retifera* Brugnone, 1880. The same Pallary, in 1920, figured a specimen of *C. elongata*, and listed the infrasubspecific names proposed as varieties of *F. retifera* by MONTEROSATO (1889): var.

Figure 5. *Chauvetia elongata* Nordsieck & García-Talavera, 1979. A-D: Marbella, Malaga, Spain, CNI (11.2 mm); E-H: 10 mm, Albufeira, Portugal, 15-20 m depth (10 mm), CRW.

Figura 5. *Chauvetia elongata* Nordsieck & García-Talavera, 1979. A-D: 11,2 mm, Marbella, Malaga, España, CNI; E-H: Albufeira, Portugal, profundidad 15-20 m (10 mm), CRW.

Figure 6. Original drawings. A: *Pleurotoma pellisphocae* Reeve, 1845. B: *Donovania (Adansonia) pellisphocae* in Pallary, 1920. C: *Chauvetia (Folinia) elongata* Nordsieck & García-Talavera, 1979.
 Figura 6. Ilustraciones originales. A: *Pleurotoma pellisphocae* Reeve, 1845. B: *Donovania (Adansonia) pellisphocae* en Pallary, 1920. C: *Chauvetia (Folinia) elongata* Nordsieck & García-Talavera, 1979.

lirifera; var. *minorglomulus* ([sic!] for *glomulus*); var. *labrosa*. The author also re-proposed the synonymy with *Lachesis dolioliformis* Monterosato, 1884. Therefore, Pallary's "*Donovania pellisphocae*" matches with *Lachesis retifera* sensu MONTEROSATO (1884, 1889), and this caused the misidentification by subsequent authors, with the arbitrary use of specific names *retifera* or *pellisphocae* for denoting *C. elongata*.

NORDSIECK (1976) treated *C. retifera* and *C. pellisphocae* as two different taxa, but both are misidentifications. The figure of *C. retifera* (fig. 39), based on a shell from Rhodes, is an eroded specimen of *Chauvetia turritellata* (Deshayes, 1835) (MICALI, 1999), while the drawing of *C. pellisphocae* (fig. 12) resembles *C. lefebvrii* (Maravigna, 1840) (MICALI, 1999). SABELLI, GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI & BEDULLI (1992) listed for the Mediterranean Sea, both *C. retifera* (Brugnone, 1880) and *C. pellisphocae* (Reeve, 1843), the latter with doubtful occurrence.

VAN AARTSEN, MENKHORST & GIT-TENBERGER (1984) treated the species as *C. pellisphocae*, and figured a specimen from the Bay of Algeciras, Spain. The authors also reported that the species does not occur in the Mediterranean Sea.

MICALI (1999) is quite controversial, because the author wrongly used the specific name *pellisphocae*, Reeve, 1845, disregarding that this name corresponds to a western Atlantic species of Pseudomelatomidae. He listed as synonyms: *L. retifera* Brugnone, 1880; *L. dolioliformis* Monterosato, 1884 and *C. elongata* Nordsieck & García-Talavera, 1979. In agreement with the old CLEMAM (Check List of European Marine Mollusca - no longer available online), Micali, without explications, split the taxon into two species, one coming from Atlantic and the other one from the Mediterranean Sea. For the latter, the author mistakenly proposed the use of *Folinia retifera* var. *lirifera* Monterosato,

1889, despite the name of Monterosato was expressly proposed as infrasubspecific rank, therefore not available, and coming from “*Casa Blanca*”, certainly not a Mediterranean area.

TRINGALI (2001) proposed, with reservations, to adopt Brugnone’s name instead of *C. pellisphocae sensu auctores*, because the original name of Reeve refers to a “*West Indian turrid*”. Without following this, GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2003) illustrated specimens of this species, from the Alboran sea, as *Chauvetia pellisphocae*.

OLIVER & ROLÁN (2008) did not write expressly about the species, but in the text they used only *C. retifera*. In OLIVER & ROLÁN (2009), *C. retifera* was quoted as separated species, without other explications in the text. The authors were unsure on the identity of *C. elongata*, because the eroded protoconch of the holotype did not allow comparison with related species. They provided a photograph photo of the holotype of *C. elongata*, but no illustration of *C. retifera*. The authors also pointed out that the holotype of *C. elongata*, most probably comes from the type locality by fishing boats, and that the species doesn’t live in the Canary Islands.

SCAPERROTTA, BARTOLINI & BOGI (2009) provided a good illustration of growth stages of the species, from the western Mediterranean Sea, but under the name *C. retifera*.

GOFAS & OLIVER (2010) also used the name of Brugnone as senior synonym *C. elongata*, and reported the misidentification of *P. pellisphocae* in PALLARY (1920). On the basis of shell morphology, the authors considered the brown form of “*C. retifera*” from the Atlantic coasts of Morocco, reported by MICALI (1999), to be most closely related to *C. lefebvrii*. They placed *Folinia retifera* var. *glomulus* Monterosato, 1889 and *Folinia retifera* var. *labrosa* Monterosato, 1889 as doubtful synonyms of *Chauvetia lefeborii* (Maravigna, 1840), while *Folinia retifera* var. *lirifera* Monterosato, 1889 as synonym of *C. retifera*, but without an objective confirmation.

VAZZANA (2010), listed *C. retifera* from Scilla, Strait of Messina, Italy, possi-

bly meaning *C. elongata*. This paper lacks many useful data: illustration; number of specimens; empty shells or living specimens; stage of the specimens. At present, this is the first and the only record for Italian waters, but without data and illustration, it must be considered doubtful or as possibly occasional.

COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011), reported for the Mediterranean Sea *C. retifera*, with *C. pellisphocae* as synonym. In HERNÁNDEZ ET AL. (2011), *C. retifera* was treated as a Mediterranean species, while the authors were uncertain about the true identity of *C. elongata*.

LANDAU & MICALI (2023), without explication, wrongly listed *C. retifera*, as living species from Mediterranean Sea, Morocco and Iberian Peninsula, and *C. pellisphocae* as living species from Mediterranean Sea and northwestern Africa.

Despite that many recent authors treated “the presumed” *Chauvetia pellisphocae* and “the improbable Recent” *Chauvetia retifera*, as separate species from Eastern Atlantic and Western Mediterranean Sea, in literature there is no evidence of this, except the double wrong identification in NORDSIECK (1976). All the figured specimens are very similar, and can refer to the same species. In addition, any author lists the possible differences in shell morphology. A potential splitting needs more deep investigations, with molecular approach and anatomical examinations.

The holotype of *C. elongata* figured by OLIVER & ROLÁN (2009) was not found in the Museo de la Naturaleza y el Hombre de Tenerife (Alejandro de Vera, comm. pers.), and is therefore probably lost. *Chauvetia elongata* is very similar to other congeneric species, and a very useful feature is the protoconch, which unfortunately is eroded in the holotype (OLIVER & ROLÁN, 2009), and not well explained in the original description. Also paratypes were not found in the RMNH, where part of collection of Bernard Zoder was added in the Naturalis collection (Jeroen Goud, comm. pers.). To stabilize the nomenclature, a neotype is here designated, with well preserved apex, and comes from Temara, Morocco.

LIST OF INVALID NAMES

- *Lachesis dolioliformis* Monterosato, 1884 (not available, IZCN art. 11.6, 12.2.1 and 12.3 - first published as a junior synonym; nomen nudum).

- *Folinia retifera* var. *lirifera* Monterosato, 1889 [sic! pro *Folineaea* Monterosato, 1884] (not available, IZCN: art. 1.3.4 and 45.5 - infrasubspecific rank; nomen dubium).

- *Folinia retifera* var. *glomulus* Monterosato, 1889 [sic! pro *Folineaea* Monterosato, 1884] (not available, IZCN: art. 1.3.4 and 45.5 - infrasubspecific rank; nomen dubium).

- *Folinia retifera* var. *labrosa* Monterosato, 1889 [sic! pro *Folineaea* Monterosato, 1884] (not available, IZCN: art. 1.3.4 and 45.5 - infrasubspecific rank; nomen dubium).

- *Lachesis doliiformis* Monterosato, 1889 [sic! misspelling pro *dolioliformis* Monterosato, 1884] (not available, IZCN art. 11.6, 12.2.1 and 12.3).

- *Donovania (Adansonia) pellisphocae* var. *minorglomulus* Monterosato in Pallary, 1920 [sic! pro *glomulus* Monterosato, 1889] (not available, nomen nudum).

- *Donovania (Adansonia) pellisphocae* var. *zonata* Pallary, 1920 (not available, IZCN: art. 1.3.4 and 45.5 - nomen nudum).

- *Donovania (Adansonia) pellisphocae* var. *lactea* Pallary, 1920 (not available, IZCN: art. 1.3.4 and 45.5 - nomen nudum).

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